

Fox Insight Parkinson's Disease Microbiome Study Sequencing Reports

Quality Control and Mapping Metrics

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1 Overview

This data dictionary documents two related datasets from the Parkinson's Disease Microbiome (PDMB) study:

1. **QC Metrics Dataset** (`qc_metrics_consented.csv`) - Sequencing quality control metrics
2. **Sample Overview Dataset** (`sample_overview_consented.csv`) - Taxonomic and functional mapping metrics

Study Details:

- **Samples:** Illumina shotgun metagenomic sequencing
- **Sample Types:** Stool and saliva samples
- **Processing:** Diversigen bioinformatics pipeline (venti-0.1.3-burst)
- **Analysis Tools:** QIIME 1.9.1

- **Filtering:** Includes only participants who provided informed consent

2 QC Metrics Dataset

File: qc_metrics_consented.csv

Description: Quality control metrics for PDMB microbiome sequencing samples including sequencing depth, quality scores, and sequence composition metrics.

2.1 Participant Identifiers

Column	Type	Description	Example
FoxDEN_ID	Character	Unique participant identifier in FoxDEN database	“FOX_928949”, “181”
sample_type	Character	Type of biological sample	“stool”, “saliva”
batch	Character	Sequencing batch date (YYYYMMDD format)	“20210322”

Note: Each participant (FoxDEN_ID) typically has two samples: one stool and one saliva sample.

2.2 Sequencing Depth Metrics

All depth metrics reported as read counts. Diversigen reports describe these as “mean sequencing depth per sample (Sample Coverage).”

Column	Type	Description
depth_raw	Numeric	Total raw sequencing reads before any processing
depth_post_cutadapt	Numeric	Reads after adapter trimming
depth_post_host_removal	Numeric	Reads after human DNA removal
depth_final_post_qc	Numeric	Final reads after trimming and quality filtering

Processing sequence: Raw reads → Adapter trimming → Host removal → Quality filtering → Final QC reads

2.3 Quality Score Metrics

Diversigen reports note that “quality scores above 25 are generally considered acceptable” and that “on Illumina sequencers quality scores always decrease toward the end of the read.”

Column	Type	Description
qscore_average_raw	Numeric	Mean quality score across all bases (raw reads)

Column	Type	Description
qscore_average_post_qc	Numeric	Mean quality score after quality filtering

2.4 Sequence Composition Metrics

Diversigen reports state that “GC content was calculated based on the raw fastqs” and “based on the trimmed and filtered fastqs.”

Column	Type	Description
gc_percentage_raw	Numeric	GC content before QC (%)
gc_percentage_post_qc	Numeric	GC content after QC (%)

2.5 PCR Duplication Metrics

Column	Type	Description
deduplicated_percentage_raw	Numeric	Percentage of unique reads before QC
deduplicated_percentage_post_qc	Numeric	Percentage of unique reads after QC

2.6 Data Filtering

Inclusion Criteria:

- Participant provided informed consent to PDMB pilot or main study
 - **Note:** Consent was re-verified for this data release. Due to time elapsed since the Fox DEN release, some participants’ consent status may have changed, resulting in dataset differences.
- Valid sample identifiers and sequencing QC metrics available
- No quality-based filtering applied (all consented samples included)

Note: Quality filtering thresholds should be determined by individual analyses based on research questions.

3 Sample Overview Dataset

File: sample_overview_consented.csv

Description: Taxonomic and functional mapping metrics showing how reads were classified to different taxonomic levels and annotated with functional information.

3.1 Participant Identifiers

Column	Type	Description	Example
FoxDEN_ID	Character	Unique participant identifier in FoxDEN database	“FOX_928949”, “181”
sample_type	Character	Type of biological sample	“stool”, “saliva”
batch	Character	Sequencing batch date (YYYYMMDD format)	“20210322”

3.2 Read Depth and Mapping Metrics

All metrics reported as read counts. These represent reads that passed all quality control filters.

3.2.1 Overall Sequencing Depth

Column	Type	Description
Read_Depth	Numeric	Total quality-filtered reads available for analysis

Note: This is equivalent to `depth_final_post_qc` from the QC metrics dataset.

3.2.2 Taxonomic Mapping

Column	Type	Description
Reads_Mapping	Numeric	Reads that mapped to microbial reference database
Reads_Genus_Level	Numeric	Reads classified to genus level or better
Reads_Species_Level	Numeric	Reads classified to species level or better
Reads_Strain_Level	Numeric	Reads classified to strain level

Observed relationship: Strain Species Genus Mapping Total reads

3.2.3 Functional Annotation

Diversigen pipeline uses KEGG Orthology (KO) annotations for functional analysis.

Column	Type	Description
Reads_KOs	Numeric	Reads assigned to KEGG Orthology (KO) functional annotations

3.3 Technical Notes

3.3.1 Processing Information

- **Pipeline version:** venti-0.1.3-burst
- **Functional databases:** kegg_venti-0.1.2-burst
- **Analysis software:** QIIME 1.9.1
- **Alignment method:** BURST